

SUSTAINABLE DESIGN FOR A FLOATING COMMUNITY IN DIANSHAN LAKE

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Abstract

Over the next century or two, sea level rise with more frequent storm surges due to climate change will invoke serious problems which are particularly foreseen in LECZ (Low-elevation coastal zone) such as lakes and riverside areas below sea level. With urbanization, coastal cities have brought numerous benefits, such as new urban development, improved transportation networks and stable sources of economic income. However, the extensive coastal development poses risks in the degradation of coastlines and their ecology. Large-scale landfill is built to extend coastal areas with hard structures to accommodate new buildings and infrastructures may have a significant impact on marine ecology.

The future strategies to accommodate water and build in coexistence with nature rather than opposing water is our objective in the future. Our research focuses on the architectural aspects of the floating community merging the gap between the planning and engineering fields. Floating platforms with modularisation and plugin units were chosen because of their flexibility to expand the needs of a community. It is basically a floating structure composed of modularized units that are interconnected on water and host all kinds of functions in order to make living on water desirable. This particular concept is developed to respond to four of the 6R's sustainable theories (Reduce*, Reuse*, Recycle, Renew, Revalue*, Reliance*). The concept proposes sustainable theory for LECZ development of a potential site which is a lake. Firstly we "Reduce" the soil in a low-lying ground through, cut and fill, the topsoil is excavated from the site and relocated so as to raise the low-elevation site above sea level. The excavated soil creates an area a few meters below the original surface level, water is let in to produce an impoundment. Subsequently, the foundations for an urban community are set afloat within the impoundment, with buildings and other facilities settled down on these floating foundations. Secondly "Reuse" is a scenario adapted for providing flexibility to change or reconfigure the functions of the floating community. The water space within the impoundment is a controlled area which can be reused based on the situation. For instance, a floating community can be reused as a research hub or a resort. Thirdly we should be mindful of "Revalue" water which can be learned from the past history and philosophy of East Asia Water towns were constructed in many parts using the water network as an effective form of transportation interconnecting the town for trade. Lastly, the fact that being dependent upon a single source water supply system and energy is not an effective "Reliance" a multi-water supply system with farming on water will become more self-sustaining efficient, economical and safe.

The paper proposes a sustainable design concept for community living in LECZ. The sustainable theory is applied in a lake to experiment with the design by applying the theories to diminish the impact of large-scale coastal land reclamation to keep a balanced ecology. The research method is identifying gaps and providing a feasible solution and how the ideology can be made more desirable for people living on water. The goal of a sustainable community is not only resilient in withstanding global environmental disasters but also to simultaneously produce a minimum burden on the environment and realise a truly sustainable community.

Keywords: Floating community, Sustainability, Coastal Lake development, Ecology

1 INTRODUCTION

Coastal areas have been attracting a significant amount of the world's population which have undergone a faster urbanization process with large migrations, causing a shortage of living space and a high cost of living (Wang & Xu, 2017). While urbanization in coastal areas has brought numerous benefits, such as new urban development, improved transportation systems and stable sources of economic income for trade. The extensive development of coastlines poses risks in the degradation of the ecology since large-scale landfill is built to extend coastal areas with "hard structures" to provide more land for new buildings and infrastructures may cause a significant impact on marine ecology (Waterman et.al 1998).

As global warming is advancing, potential sea level rise, along with more frequent heavy rain due to severe typhoons would cause flooding in low-elevation coastal zones and increase the salinity of rivers and lakes. At this point, it is necessary to prepare for this scenario as large areas of land will get inundated by water. Proper resilience of architectural buildings to counter these natural disasters is needed. The new tendency of living indicates that people enjoy living in comfortable, peaceful housing with nature and most importantly keeping a strong sense of community (Moon, 2015). Therefore, a new typology of housing communities will be proposed to address climate change as well as fulfil the social needs of a growing number of people who live at risk in low-elevation coastal zones.

In this future scenario, floating architecture is among the resolutions for our resilience against flooding in many coastal cities around the world. Various types of designs for floating architecture already existed since past civilizations. The construction technique and architecture of these buildings vary in different regions depending on the climatic conditions, the culture and the raw materials available at the local places. In Europe the historical evolution is relatively simple, initially, there were houseboats which in many cases were originally used as ships. While in Asia there has been a longer history of floating villages (Stopp & Strangfeld, 2010). Floating buildings are designed to float on water and utilize the space of seas, rivers, and lakes. Compared with traditional anchored houseboats, modern floating houses are designed for high-quality living spaces and are arranged in regulated urban planning which functions similarly to buildings on land (Wang & Xu, 2017). However, what is lacking from the past design is an urban design philosophy for floating community therefore it is essential to develop urban design principles that are specifically accustomed to a community. This includes solutions for public space, facilities, mobility, densities, water space use and above all the possible way of living for a floating community (Graaf, 2012).

2 METHODOLOGY

The paper proposes sustainable design and planning principles of a floating community based on data collected from a selected case study to identify key components of sustainable theory for a floating community. The research by design aims to provide sustainable theory on the following key aspects:

- 1) The spatial planning
- 2) The spatial pattern for the community
- 3) Modular floating building design structure

Plans, sections, maps and photos will be used as a major method to analyse and illustrate the design concept.

3 LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Living on Water

Living on water provides numerous benefits in the planning of sustainable design, for instance:

(1) Its responses to the rise of sea levels, (2) It preserves the lack of land for agriculture and provides space for housing and commercial growth, (3) It creates new and innovative ideas for touristic destinations, (4) The building footprint is much smaller than land-based constructions, (5) Densely populated city built near the waterbodies can be extended on water (Lin et al., 2018).

Water also has profound meaning in atmospheric and visual qualities that enhance the living experience. The Greeks used artificial basins to embellish their springs for social practices, while the Chinese, water is an idealized natural world that has a regenerative and visual role. Waterscape enhances the moods from serene lakes and pounding sea waves that create opportunities for leisure activities (Wylson, 1988).

Although the idea of living on water has a promising concept for solving intricate social, environmental and planning problems. The conflicting demand in developing modern floating buildings needs to function as a typical building on land in terms of comfort, quality and affordability. Comfort means that the stability and building functions similarly to those on land, for example, the availability of outdoor spaces for gardening, parking and accessibility increases the comfort of residents. In terms of quality, the materials and maintenance required for floating buildings should have a similar life span as regular buildings on land. At present, floating buildings are still a relatively new market and the price is higher, especially in a single project. Therefore, in order to make it competitive with buildings on land, the project should be built in larger quantities through prefabrication and mass production (Olthuis, 2010).

3.2 Planning Aspects of Legislation

The current situation of water-based dwellings remains a new concept for spatial planning. At present the laws and regulations have limitations applicable to water-based dwellings which expose challenges for realising this concept (Indah, 2013). Building law generally stipulates that all buildings must be directly connected to the land. For this reason, even if the floaters are directly in contact with land using poles under the water, the fact that they are on the water, it is unlikely that they will be admitted permanently as part of a building site. A possible way to admit buildings on water as a building site for residential or commercial purposes is by using dykes to enclose and control the water space. Simultaneously the flooded land surface may allow the water area to be treated as a public space by the local government. There exist several related laws for the design of floating structures such as architectural law, the law covering fire safety, the law of the road, harbour law, ship design law, the law of transportation and so on. The effective application of appropriate laws will be adjusted and decided by the government divisions (Nakajima & Umeyama 2007).

3.3 Large-Scale Coastal Reclamation

The need for expanding the land area of coastal cities on the water is eventually an uncontrollable method to accommodate new buildings. This method is regarded being unsustainable since new land is created by filling with sand mass in the water pushing away water which destroys the underwater ecosystem. In addition, the new land extension interferes with the water currents, for instance, that case was discovered after the construction of the Palm Jumeirah in UAE. It became clear that the surrounding coasts were affected by the landfills which altered the water currents. Rotterdam dredging company Van Oord responsible for constructing Palm Jumeirah had to intervene in the problem that arose. The height of the coast was raised with extra breakwater to save the surrounding coastline. Other problems caused are the increase in salinity of water and the rise in temperature as the evaporative cooling effect is affected. Another drawback is that landfill needs a longer construction period to settle down and strengthen the foundation in order to build on it. Lastly is sourcing a tremendous amount of stone and sand for landfills which is an unsustainable practice (Olthuis, 2010).

3.4 Impoundment on Low-Elevation

“Room for the Rivers (2005) and Working Together with Water (2008)” are the approaches for urban development that integrate spatial planning with water management in the national spatial policy of the Netherlands. Rather than pushing the water back to the sea or protecting the low-elevation land by building higher walls, water is accommodated as much as possible in surrounding urban areas landscapes. The water management policy specifies that new residential neighbourhoods in low elevations are required to provide at least 10% water surface for storage during floods (Indah, 2013). Creating impoundment on low-elevation coastal zones increases the capacity of lakes and rivers as it opens more room for water when the sea level rises. It also acts as a water storage while allocating space to accommodate new buildings. The impoundment is built using dykes creating a buffer zone which keeps the floating buildings in a safe zone. This method is a possible solution for legislature problems and may consider the water area as a building site. It allows structures to be built on water space that functions and regulates similarly to the ones on land.

3.5 Floating Community Case Study

IJ-Lake has a collection of floating houses built on 6 artificial islands in the eastern part of Amsterdam, it has been the first to make the largest floating community. The vision is to solve the city's critical housing shortage and flooding problems as it is the most urbanized region in the Netherlands (Indah, 2013). The planning goal will develop 18,000 homes for 45,000 residents with 30% among low-income residents and create around 12,000 jobs on 10 islands after completion (Srinivas et al., 2022). Among these islands, the IJburg's Waterbuurt is worth learning from, with residential and mixed-use development built in 2012. The

community is composed of 165 floating houses, apartment blocks that include parking on land and offices equipped with inlet water level control (Ballegooijen et al., 2012). The site is divided into two areas Waterbuurt East and Waterbuurt West (Fig.1a). The west side (3) is composed of 3 piles and 55 floating houses designed by an architect, Marlies Rohmer. On the east side (4) of the site, a capacity of 110 floating buildings is reserved for private development, where the owners can design their own floating houses. This project is the only floating building that is considered as 'real estate' property by the government, unlike boat houses these properties are not free to move, the regulations are also complied with this project such as safety, public access maintenance and utilities (Indah, 2013).

Fig. 1a Waterbuurt Masterplan with mixed building typologies (Source: author)

Sustainable design strategies		
Social	Ecology	Planning
The piers are made public	Floating units reduce the footprint on soil	Parking facilities, boat dock electricity and water utilities
Mixed-use with a diverse program	Sewage for water quality control	Flexibility of movable units
Variety of housing typology for different social class	Water storage	Interconnected piers
Use water space as shared social space	Safe material selection	Mixed structural types, floating, on the land and piles

Fig. 1b Sustainable design strategies (Source: author)

The planning and building design have well integrated the complexities of living on water. On the other hand, the major criticism is the lack of green spaces within the Waterbuurt inlet. It was a deliberate decision from the municipal designers as they believed gardens would not suit the urban visual aesthetic of the neighbourhood. Due to the limited width of the jetties, plants and trees cannot be integrated into the marine environment. Also, a minimum ratio of 20% of the plot has to remain open water, so the limited proportion of space available does not allow the capacity to allocate gardens or terraces (Ballegooijen et al., 2012). Not all the residents of the houses share the same view so instead they have attached floating gardens and flowerpots to satisfy their need for greenery (Fig. 1c)

Fig. 1c Greenery installed by the residents (Source: Maarschalk, 2022).

4 SUSTAINABLE STRATEGY FOR FLOATING COMMUNITY

To create a sustainable floating community that is safe and comfortable to live in, the design should be socially environmentally and economically inclusive. In order to ensure that the goals and users' needs are met, the strategy envisioned is to apply the sustainable theories Reduce*, Reuse*, Recycle, Renew, Revalue* and Reliance*. Reduce essentially addresses the environmental issues, Reuse provides economical solutions, and Revalue and Reliance aim at targeting social goals.

4.1 Reduce the Soil

Reducing the land of the site is one of the key sustainable concepts to build with nature as it reduces the building footprint on land. It also provides a safe room for storing storm water which creates a buffer zone for the community to live comfortably on water. Since the use of walls to protect coastal cities in many cases has experienced damage due to erosion. Consequently, replacing and reinforcing the seawalls has become necessary despite the high costs, however considering for a long-term view, it is inevitable sea level rise will subsequently increase the height of walls. Therefore, it is impractical to replace or reinforce all the walls in low-elevation coastal zones as it is not efficient and cost-effective (Nakajima & Umeyama 2007). So, the resilient solution envisioned for the next 50 or 100 years is to adapt the Low-Elevation Coastal Zone to sea level rise by accommodating and living with water.

4.2 Reuse the Water Space for Other Functions

Reuse is a scenario capable of readapting by providing the flexibility to change or reconfigure the program of a floating community. The water space within the impoundment is a controlled area which can be reused based on the current situation. For instance, a floating community can be reused as a research hub or a resort, it also allows the flexibility to expand or contract therefore controlling its density. Floating buildings can be removed if they are not needed anymore and they can begin a new life at a different location. The idea is to use water space instead of land which has the advantage of building a short-term event. After that, the water space can be quickly taken for another program.

An effective way of reuse is through modularisation of building constructions offers a possible solution for producing more cheaper and energy-efficient. Therefore, using modular units is a sustainable strategy to build a flexible floating structure. It is a quick method to lift up and replace with the desired space

4.3 Revalue Water Transportation

A philosophic approach that we should be mindful of "Revalue" water which can be learned from the past history of East Asia water-town and floating villages were constructed in many parts using the water network as an effective form of transportation interconnecting the town for trade. The idea is to widen the transportation options through water network. This could be realized by living close to water and ultimately promoting the use of water transportation. For example, water transportation in Venice has been maintained as the only alternative to walking but other European cities has remained highly reliant on vehicular transportation resulting in traffic dominance (Wylson,1988).

4.4 Reliance on Resources from Land

We build on water to preserve enough farmland for agriculture and natural scenery, especially in densely populated areas where land is limited, this is a critical aspect for preserving food resources and raw materials from land (Graaf, 2012). Being dependent upon a single-source water supply system, energy and agriculture from land is not an effective “Reliance”. A multi-water supply system with farming on water will become more self-sustaining efficient, economical and safe.

5 PROJECT BACKGROUND

Urbanization in China has driven the population towards the coastal cities since its economic growth in recent decades among these coastal cities Shanghai has the largest population living in the LECZ (McGranahan et al., 2007). Shanghai is known as a massive city in the south of the Yangtze River with an extensive water network typically known as manmade canals with around 80% of the area in Shanghai falling within the water network. The streets and lanes crisscross the water network with numerous bridges. Docks, ferries and agricultural fields are separated on the outskirts of the city. The Huangpu River is one of the streams that enter at the mouth of the Yangtze River, it runs through the city downtown and it is sourced from a series of interconnected lakes in the western suburbs of Shanghai (Fig. 3). Dianshan Lake is an important water body of Huangpu River as it is the largest freshwater lake in the city and it is one of the major navigation channels for trade (Fig.4). This lake has a rich fishery resource and its beautiful scenery home many historic sites with small fishing villages, making it a popular destination for leisure activities as well as high economic values (Kindong et al., 2017). The existing practices of the transformation of the lake by reducing the land to accommodate more water in the lake can be seen in Figure 5.

Fig. 3 Site relation with Yangtze River through Huangpu River (Source: author)

Fig. 4 Trade route across Dianshan Lake

Fig. 5 Dianshan Lake expansion protected with dykes (Source: google earth)

5.1 Objectives Living on Water

The urban conditions of the city today are multifaceted with abundant opportunities for social, cultural, and economic growth. Water is a resource that could be rethought as Shanghai is abundant in water resources which play a major role in its development. The existing water network provides a convenient means of transportation, and more importantly, it can satisfy the need for leisure activities close to the city. As the high-tier city is growing the demand for green spaces and leisure activities are highly desirable. The idea of living on the water creates the opportunity for the citizen to enjoy comfortable, peaceful housing with nature while keeping a strong sense of community and ultimately a new experience for their well-being.

Building on water has dual functions towards sustainable community, firstly it is a flood-resilient concept and secondly, its key objective is to reduce inner-city population density. Dianshan Lake has the opportunity to address these issues, by taking the space of the lake near urban areas, this method can provide a more affordable area for living to help ease some of the housing demand in Shanghai. Also, this approach can be an alternative method of land reclamation instead of opposing water due to sea level rise, as more room is open to accommodate water. Living on water is worth to synthesis the development of a sustainable model which is the key objective for resilience in the future, thus reducing the impact on the next generation.

5.2 Sustainable Model

Based on the research findings from the literature review, the design proposes a sustainable model by implementing the 4Rs theories at Dianshan Lake. The design proposal shows the approach for the site preparation, spatial planning with the preconditioned systems that organise the community and lastly the removable units that are flexible to be relocated and the water space is then reused for different situations. Temporary functions such as a research laboratory can be reused as a housing accommodation and resort for tourist attractions. Seasonal events such as sports competitions can be allocated on water and dismantled quickly after the event. The ability to cultivate food both on land and water could be the solution for food limitations in the future.

5.2.1 Site preparation

Step 1. The topsoil is excavated from the site through, cut and fill, the soil is relocated so as to raise the low-elevation site above sea level the excavated soil creates an inlet area a few meters below the original surface level. Dykes are built to prevent the destruction of the shoreline and it creates a safe impoundment for the community (Fig. 6a). The area inside the dykes is then flooded until the water level inside reached the same level as the lake with its surrounding river and sea. The water shoreline is adapted to create an ecological threshold that improves and regulates the water quality.

LOW ELEVATION SITE

RAISED SITE

Fig. 6a Reduce soil to provide room for water (Source: author)

Step 2. The site is divided based on the programming needs. An urban grid is placed which regulates the space into a humanly scaled space and, subsequently the allocation of the facilities, access and density of water space use for a floating community. Major roads are extended to the lake so as to activate the vitality

of the community. Green belts are inserted within the impoundment to restore the ecology, it also improves the landscape scenery which enhances the spatial quality for water sports activities within the community (Fig. 6b).

Program distribution

Generating grid with axis

Expansion of community

Ecology restoration

Fig. 6b Site planning strategies (Source: author)

Step 3. Prefabricated units are subsequently moved and set afloat in the impoundment. For larger buildings modular components are assembled on floating foundations. Floating foundations are prefabricated at shipbuilding facilities and are towed to the sites. This method is shown in Fig. 6c, the floating foundation keeps itself afloat but in addition a "Soft-Landing System" is added to this system, the floating foundations are semi-supported by piles constructed underneath in case the water level drops too low where the water depth is not deep enough to enable the foundation to float.

Fig. 6c Large building floating foundation (Source: Nakajima, 2007)

5.2.2 Spatial planning

Based on different scenarios 2 preconditioned systems have been proposed for the possible way of life for floating communities. Both systems follow a linear organisation that is extended from the land to the water.

TYPE A is a dense planning that occupies a small area of water space. The spatial hierarchy is reinforced by a major avenue connecting and providing access to a strong community. The avenue acts as a spine that connects the land to the water allowing vehicle and pedestrian access which becomes a commercial and leisure corridor. Diverse mix-use functions are inserted, a commercial entity of offices, guest's hotel, market and street food with a series of interconnected pavilions and canopies. The idea is to create a highly walkable floating community and a catalyst to allow serendipitous encounters between the local people and visitors. The program starts with an open space market, worker's canteen, offices, boutique hotels, apartments with parking facilities and a cafeteria (Fig.7a). Last but not least the structural types are mixed combining piles and floating buildings have been chosen for their efficiency.

TYPE B is a decentralised planning condition, the idea is to create a serene atmosphere that offers more space for the community to breathe and perform activities. This scheme allows higher flexibility for reconfiguration as certain types of units are individually floating on water. Likewise, green belts are interweaved in the community through walkways that enhance the spatial quality as all residents can get access to these green spaces. The floating sphere on the lake became one of the main gatherings with entertaining activities.

Fig. 7a TYPE A with vehicle and pedestrian access (Source: author)

Fig. 7b TYPE B flexible floating units (Source: author)

5.2.3 Modular units

Modular units for the TYPE A community use standard dimensions of shipping containers to allow quick assembly on-site since these units are customized at the factory (Fig. 8a). Modular units for the TYPE B community are designed like a houseboat with all the facilities needed to live comfortably as a house on land (Fig. 8b)

Fig. 8a Modularized units 6mx2.5mx2.9m (Source: author)

Fig. 8b Floating units

6 CONCLUSION

This project has brought us to the idea that living on water can be a solution for our current housing issues and the future way of living with challenges faced in populated cities due to sea level rise. Although plenty of floating houses already exist in many cities such as Amsterdam, the bigger projects proposed by professional architectural firms are usually unrealized, since this concept has a niche market. As we have seen from the case study analysis which lacks some characteristics, this design proposal can fill those gaps by providing green spaces and a driveway for better accessibility and comfort to the residents. Water gives us diverse opportunities, first of all, it is important to go beyond a single function of residential use and provide other functions and activities for the community that can essentially promote its growth.

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